

Expanding Collaborative Technologies in Rural Veteran Health Care Using Tele-robotic Stroke Therapy Delivery and Monitoring Systems

Colleen O'Brien Cherry, Laura M. Tilghman
University of Georgia
Athens, GA, USA
cobrien@uga.edu tilghman@uga.edu

Kimberly Richards, David Wu, Andrew Butler
Georgia State University
Atlanta, GA, USA
krichards@gsu.edu dwu@gsu.edu andrewbutler@gsu.edu

Neale R. Chumbler
Western Kentucky University
Bowling Green, KY, USA
Neale.chumbler@wku.edu

Amber Huff
Institute of Development Studies
Brighton, UK
a.huff@ids.ac.uk

POSTER EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Abstract—This poster reports on a qualitative evaluation of a tele-robotic stroke therapy delivery and monitoring system intervention.

Keywords—telehealth, robotics, physical therapy, rural, qualitative, stroke rehabilitation.

I. PROBLEM CONSIDERED

Rural veterans make up a growing percentage of total veterans using the Veterans Health Administration (VHA) system [1]. Approximately 3.2 million rural veterans are receiving care from VHA representing 36% of the total veteran enrolled population [1]. Rural veterans have greater healthcare needs, lower quality of life scores, and experience higher rates of physical illness in comparison to their urban counterparts. However, despite their greater needs, rural veterans are less likely to access health services, often due to travel barriers including lack of public transportation and greater distance to care [2]. One of the major problems in the US health care system for stroke survivors is the inability to provide quality post-stroke rehabilitation [3]. Applications of Telehealth, which integrates information and communication technologies, have been proposed as a cost effective solution to increase access to care in rural areas [4]. Randomized controlled trials in telehealth have demonstrated its effectiveness for patients and results indicate that telerobotic therapy provides consistent and reproducible treatment [5,6]. Few if any studies to our knowledge have assessed rural veterans' general impressions on effectiveness, benefits, and barriers of using robotic therapy devices for in-home rehabilitation.

II. OBJECTIVES

The aim of this study is to improve access and quality of care for rural veterans by developing evidence-based and

innovative practices to support the unique needs of veterans who reside in geographically remote areas.

III. RESEARCH APPROACH AND METHODS

Participants formed a convenience sample and were introduced to the project by their clinician, who was their primary care doctor, nurse practitioner, or physical therapist at the VA Hospital or CBOC where they accessed care. If the patient expressed interest in using one of the telerobotic devices, their clinician contacted the telerehabilitation team who then discussed participation with the patient. The prospective participants were given a description of the project and asked if they would be willing to have a home visit and participate in an interview on their experiences using the device after they completed their therapy. The ten study participants were veterans aged 45-90 who had experienced a unilateral ischemic or hemorrhagic stroke.

Figure 1 (left): Hand Mentor™ device and monitor.

Figure 2 (right): Monitor with display of game.

Once participants' eligibility was verified and they became enrolled in the program, they were granted use of an

in-home robotic rehabilitation device (Kinetic Muscles, Inc. Tempe, AZ 85282). Individuals with residual upper limb impairments were given a Hand Mentor™ device (see Figure 1), while individuals with residual lower limb impairments were given the Foot Mentor™. The device is comprised of a hand or foot peripheral component wired into a processing unit containing the pneumatic pump and a touchscreen interface with a monitor that displayed games that the participant would play using the hand or foot mentor essentially as the joystick. The device also has a cellular modem so that data from the therapy could be sent to a secure server to be monitored by a therapist. The device is powered through a wall-outlet.

We used a qualitative study design employing ethnographic-based methods to assess veterans' impressions on effectiveness, benefits, and barriers of using these robotic therapy devices for rehabilitation delivery. Research methods included direct observation of the in-home environment and in-depth semi-structured interviews (see Table 1). Veterans and their caregivers were observed and interviewed shortly after the telerobotic stroke therapy was completed. Afterwards, thematic analysis was conducted using an inductive approach.

TABLE 1 QUALITATIVE RESEARCH METHODS

Direct Observation Protocol
1. Accessibility and distance from VAMC or CBOC?
2. Home environment—caregiver support for assistance with the device?
3. Space to setup the device?
4. Electrical outlet for the device?
5. Table and chair to use the device?
Interview Guide
1. Tell me about your experience using the robotic [arm or leg] device. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Where do you usually use it? ○ What time of day? ○ For how long each session/day? ○ How do you feel during or after using the robotic device? ○ What else can you tell us about using the robotic device?
2. What are some of the things that you like about using the device?
3. What are some of the things that you do not like about using the device?
4. In what ways is using the robotic device different than going to physical therapy sessions at the VA or CBOC?
5. If you could change something about the device, what would it be?

IV. TECHNICAL CHALLENGES

Barriers to use of the telerobotic stroke technology by veteran patients were few and included difficulties with placing the device on the body, bulkiness of the monitor, and modem connection problems.

V. RESULTS AND ACCOMPLISHMENTS

Participants reported positive experiences with the robotic stroke therapy delivery and monitoring system,

despite some technical challenges with the devices. The themes identified in interviews and observations in this qualitative study showed that patients responded both to the direct physical impact of the intervention, as well as the indirect benefits such as an improvement in mood that were made possible by physical improvements from rehabilitation. Examples of these benefits include feeling more mobile, having an outlet for mental tension and anxiety, experiencing an improved mind-body connection, and becoming more independent. Patients also responded positively to the way in which rehabilitation was delivered by the home-based robotic device itself, such as having control over the timing and duration of the rehabilitation therapy sessions, and avoiding the cost and time involved with travel to do physical therapy in a clinical setting.

VI. EXPECTED CONTRIBUTIONS AND SIGNIFICANCE

Use of the telerobotic devices allowed for extended in home therapy. Based on research results, the manufacturing company is working on modifying the devices to be less cumbersome, more user-friendly, and more adaptable to participants' homes. Our findings have also directed us to modify the treatment protocol by extending the usage period past 3 months until the patient plateaus in progress or no longer wants to use the device.

VII. IMPACT AND CONCLUSIONS

Telerehabilitation robotic devices can be used as a tool to extend effective, evidence-based, and specialized rehabilitation services for upper and lower limb rehabilitation to rural Veterans with poor access to care.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to thank all of the veterans and their families and caregivers who participated in their interviews for this project. The funding for this project was through the Veteran's Administration Office of Rural Health, project number is NO7-FY13Q1-S1-P00621.

REFERENCES

- [1] Office of Rural Health, "About rural veterans," 2014. <http://www.ruralhealth.va.gov/about/rural-veterans.asp>
- [2] M. S. Phipps, et al., "Rural-urban differences in inpatient quality of care in US veterans with ischemic stroke," *J Rural Health*, vol. 30, pp. 1-6, 2014.
- [3] L. Schwamm, et al., "A review of the evidence for the use of telemedicine within stroke systems of care: a scientific statement from the American Heart Association/American Stroke Association," *Stroke*, vol. 40, pp. 2616-2634, 2009.
- [4] A. J. Butler, et al., "Expanding tele-rehabilitation of stroke through in-home robot-assisted therapy," *Int J Phys Med Rehabil*, vol. 2, n. 184, pp. 1-11, 2014.
- [5] N. G. Kutner, R. Zhang, A. J. Butler, S. L. Wolf, J. L. Roberts, "Quality-of-life change associated with robotic-assisted therapy to improve hand motor function in patients with subacute stroke: a randomized clinical trial," *Phys Ther*, vol. 90, pp. 493-504, 2010.
- [6] A.C. Lo, et al., "Robot-assisted therapy for long-term upper-limb impairment after stroke," *N Engl J Med*, vol. 362, pp. 1772-1783, 2010.